

USING AUDIO-LINGUAL METHOD TO IMPROVING LISTENING SKILLS OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract: teacher listening comprehension educational Introduction is a medium of communication, which helps the members of a community in the society, to communicate and interact with one another. This involves both verbal and non-verbal communication. Language focuses on listening and reading that can be named as passive or receptive skills, while speaking and writing can be named as, active or productive skills. Listening is one of the important skills in learning a language. The process of acquiring a language starts with listening and ends up in the production of writing. After birth, a child hears variety of sounds and can distinguish among them. Every language has a common and a natural sequence for the development of the language skills. Listening skill is ranked first of all the four folds. This highlights the importance of listening skill in the life of human beings. Students normally face and encounter listening problems especially in foreign languages paper presents arguments for an emphasis on listening comprehension in language learning/teaching. An explanation of how listeners can use strategies to enhance the learning process is presented, with a review of the existing research base on how second language listening is taught. The major part of the paper presents and discusses pedagogical recommendations and speaking are often taught together, but beginners, especially non-literate ones, should be given more listening than speaking practice. It's important to speak as close to natural speed as possible, although with beginners some slowing is usually necessary. Without reducing speaking speed it is possible to make a language easier to comprehend by simplifying vocabulary, using shorter sentences, and increasing the number and length of pauses in speech the importance of listening in language learning and teaching it is essential for language teachers to help their students become effective listeners. In the communicative approach to language teaching, this means modeling listening strategies and providing listening practice in authentic situations: those that learners are likely to encounter when they use the language outside the classroom.

Key words: listening, interactive, develop, sticks, content, teaching, interest, approach.

Teaching listening skills is one of the most difficult tasks for any teacher. Successful listening skills are acquired over time and with lots of practice. It's rather complicated for students because there are no definite rules. Listening is the ability to identify and understand what others are saying. This involves understanding a speaker's accent or pronunciation, his grammar and his vocabulary, and grasping his meaning (Howatt and Dakin). An able listener is capable of doing these four things simultaneously.

Listening is one of the fundamental language skills. It's a medium through which children, young people and adults gain a large portion of their education-- their information, their understanding of the world and of human affairs, their ideals, sense of values, and their appreciation. Listening involves many other basic processes such as linguistic competence, previous knowledge that is not necessarily of a purely linguistic nature. Lack of social, cultural, factual, and contextual knowledge of the target language can present an obstacle to listening comprehension and it can cause a lot of difficulties.

Here we can speak about a mental block. While listening a student may not understand what is being said and he starts panicking. At this point, many students just tune out or get caught up in an internal dialogue trying to translate a specific word. They get distracted and it creates problems. The role of a teacher then is to convince them that not understanding is OK. Only practice makes it perfect.

Students need to listen to English as often as possible. Encourage them to get a film, or listen to an English radio station. Students should often listen, but they should listen for short periods - five to ten minutes, four or five times a week. Even if they don't understand anything, five to ten minutes is a must for those who want to improve their skills in listening comprehension. Still it won't happen too quickly as it requires time. Principles of the Audio-Lingual Method
The native language and the target language have separate linguistic systems. They should be kept apart so that the students' native language interferes as little as possible with the students' attempts to acquire the target language. (The language teacher uses only the target language in the classroom. Actions, pictures are used to give meaning otherwise). One of the language teacher's major roles is that of a model of the target language. Teachers should provide students with a native-speaker-like model. By listening to how it is supposed to sound, students should be able to mimic the model (The language teacher introduces the dialogue by modeling it two times; she introduces the drills by modeling the correct answers; at other times, she

corrects mispronunciation by modeling the proper sounds in the target language). Language learning is a process of habit formation. The more often something is repeated, the stronger the habit and the greater the learning. Pattern practice help students to form habits which enable the students to use the We do not need to memorize rules in order to use our native language. The rules necessary to use the target language will be figured out or induced from examples (Students are given no grammar rules; grammatical points are taught through examples and drills).

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